

Strategic Leadership and 4IR Technologies in R&D: Analysis of Innovation Barriers in South Africa's Pharmaceutical Sector

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Abstract. The increasing adoption of technologies associated with the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), such as artificial intelligence (AI) and biotechnology, presents opportunities for enhancing research and development (R&D), and innovation within pharmaceutical organisations. This study examines the relationship between R&D intensity, strategic leadership, and the adoption of 4IR technologies in South Africa's pharmaceutical sector. Using a quantitative approach, survey data was collected from industry professionals and key decision makers, yielding 78 valid responses. Findings indicate that while emerging 4IR technologies are important, they alone do not drive strategic innovation. Their success depends on effective integration into existing frameworks, with top management support playing a crucial role. Barriers such as technological gaps, regulatory delays, and skill shortages hinder technology adoption. The weak link between technology capability and innovation highlights the need for stronger digital literacy and aligned leadership. Pharmaceutical organisations should integrate technologies with leadership-driven R&D strategies, while policymakers should focus on regulatory reforms and incentives. This study provides insights into technology, leadership, and R&D in emerging healthcare markets, calling for further research on digital transformation's long-term impact.

Keywords: 4IR, Pharmaceutical R&D, Innovation Barriers, Strategic Leadership, Technology Adoption.

1 Introduction

The global pharmaceutical market valuation was an estimated US\$1.6 trillion in 2023, with projections estimating that it will reach US\$1.9 trillion by 2027. The United States dominates this sector, accounting for nearly 40% of the global pharmaceutical market [1]. To support these market developments, organisations in the pharmaceutical industry are leveraging technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) to drive their digital transformation strategies [2, 3]. Technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), biotechnology, and big data analytics are being adopted across the business units to reshape drug discovery, optimise clinical trials and healthcare delivery, allowing pharmaceutical stakeholders to enhance research and development (R&D) efficiency [4]. Emerging healthcare markets are also expanding rapidly. In South Africa, the pharmaceutical industry is the largest in Sub-Saharan Africa, valued at ZAR157.14 trillion

in 2023, and is projected to grow [5]. However, as global competition intensifies, leveraging technological innovation is no longer a luxury but a necessity to enhance drug development pipelines, improve regulatory compliance, and ensure sustainable business practices [4, 6–9], to name a few. In this context, the effective adoption of 4IR technologies is a critical success factor in the future of pharmaceutical R&D and market competitiveness [2].

4IR technologies offer a strategic avenue to overcome challenges and existing latencies. For instance, AI can accelerate drug discovery by processing vast biomedical datasets, while biotechnology facilitates advancements in precision medicine, personalised drug formulations, and biopharmaceutical production [6]. Despite these transformative potentials, the integration of these technologies in South African pharmaceutical organisations remains irregular. Several structural barriers hinder widespread adoption, including limited technological infrastructure, regulatory constraints, and resource limitations [10, 11]. There is also a limited talent pool due to the migration of skills [12]. Addressing these challenges requires a strategic level understanding of how organisations adopt and integrate 4IR technologies within their business information systems, yet this remains an underexplored area in the South African pharmaceutical sector.

Extensive research has examined the role of R&D investment in pharmaceutical innovation, highlighting its impact on market sustainability, competitive advantage, and breakthrough drug formulations [4, 6, 13]. However, there remains a gap in empirical research on how South African pharmaceutical organisations integrate 4IR technologies into their R&D process [4]. Existing studies predominantly focus on developed markets, lacking a clear understanding of how emerging economies like South Africa navigate digital transformation in R&D [9]. This gap presents an opportunity to explore how the integration of advanced technologies, such as AI and biotechnology, can enhance R&D outcomes and contribute to the sector's growth and competitiveness in the South African context.

The Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) framework [14] provides a structured approach to examining technology adoption in pharmaceutical organisations by considering three key dimensions. The first is (i) technological context, which explores the role of AI, biotechnology, and data analytics in R&D. Secondly, (ii) organisational context, which assesses how internal factors such as leadership commitment, workforce capability, and investment in R&D determine the extent of technological integration [3]. Finally, (iii) environmental context considers external influences, such as regulatory compliance, industry competition, and public health challenges [15]. To this effect, the TOE framework is advantageous in identifying key enablers and barriers to technology adoption in pharmaceutical R&D. However, it does not always explain how these technologies diffuse within the industry. Due to this limitation, the Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) theory [16] was considered, which focuses on how innovations spread within one sector [17–19]. This is because in the South African pharmaceutical sector, the DOI framework is relevant in understanding the adoption of AI and biotechnology. These technologies offer relative advantages as they enhance drug discovery and precision medicine [4]. However, compatibility challenges exist, particularly concerning integrating with existing R&D infrastructure and aligning with regulatory

frameworks. The complexity of implementing AI-driven drug discovery presents another barrier, given that it requires advanced expertise and computational resources that may not be readily available in resource-constrained settings [20]. Despite the insights provided by DOI, its applicability to pharmaceutical R&D in South Africa remains limited. Unlike consumer-driven industries where innovations diffuse rapidly, pharmaceutical R&D is characterised by long product development cycles, stringent regulatory scrutiny, and substantial capital investments, which slows the diffusion process [4, 21]. Additionally, the interaction between organisational leadership, regulatory policies, and economic constraints in shaping adoption decisions requires deeper empirical analysis.

Consequently, this study explores the impact of R&D intensity and leadership decision-making on innovation outcomes, focusing on the role of 4IR technologies as enablers or barriers to technological transformation in South Africa's pharmaceutical sector. The central research question guiding this investigation is "*How does R&D intensity impact strategic and innovative decisions within the South African pharmaceutical industry?*".

To achieve this, a quantitative research design is adopted, incorporating industry surveys and data analytics to assess how South African pharmaceutical organisations are adopting 4IR technologies. The research is grounded in the TOE updated for 4IR technologies [19], with data collected from pharmaceutical executives, R&D professionals, and industry stakeholders.

This study aligns with global efforts to leverage 4IR technologies for enhanced healthcare outcomes, contributing to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Good Health and Well-being and Industry (SDG 3), Innovation, and Infrastructure (SDG 9).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature on pharmaceutical R&D and 4IR technologies, Section 3 details the research methodology, Section 4 notes findings, and Section 5 and 6 encompass the discussion with implications for industry and policy and concluding thoughts.

2 Background

The South African pharmaceutical sector significantly contributes to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and remains the most developed in Sub-Saharan Africa. Novartis, a JSE-listed pharmaceutical company, contributed over three billion rand to the South African economy in 2018. From 2013 to 2023, pharmaceutical sales have more than doubled, with projections estimating industry growth to reach approximately R48 billion. As of the fourth quarter of 2023, the pharmaceutical sector accounted for 1.04% of South Africa's GDP, which stood at R1.15 trillion [22]. These figures highlight the industry's economic significance and role in supporting national health policies and industrial development.

Despite its economic importance, the sector faces structural and technological challenges that hinder its ability to effectively leverage 4IR technologies. The industry's reliance on traditional pharmaceutical processes and regulatory barriers limits its capacity for rapid technological integration. While the global pharmaceutical industry has

embraced digital transformation, mainly through AI, biotechnology, and data analytics, South Africa's pharmaceutical organisations have lagged in implementing these technologies due to financial and regulatory constraints [8, 15].

2.1 Industry Dynamics and Barriers

Technological advancements have transformed pharmaceutical industries worldwide, enabling more efficient drug discovery, personalised medicine, and AI-driven research processes [2, 4]. However, the South African pharmaceutical sector has exhibited stagnation in its technological evolution, with organisations continuing to rely on conventional R&D methodologies rather than fully adopting 4IR technologies [10, 11]. The reluctance to transition towards digitally enabled health solutions has resulted in inefficiencies that affect drug development cycles and market competitiveness. Key trends in global pharmaceutical innovation indicate a growing reliance on biotechnology, AI-assisted drug development, and regulatory shifts that encourage digital integration [3]. South Africa, however, faces significant challenges in aligning with these trends. Regulatory constraints, financial limitations, and resistance to technological change have emerged as primary obstacles to successfully implementing AI-driven solutions and biotechnological advancements [11]. The stringent regulatory frameworks that govern pharmaceutical innovations in South Africa delay the approval and commercialisation of new technologies, creating a restrictive backlog towards R&D expansion. Additionally, ethical considerations surrounding AI in drug development further complicate regulatory approvals, preventing organisations from fully leveraging emerging technologies. Financial constraints present another major challenge, as implementing AI and biotechnology in R&D requires substantial capital investment, which many pharmaceutical companies are reluctant to undertake due to perceived financial risks [23]. Studies indicate that many organisations remain sceptical about the cost-benefit ratio of 4IR technology adoption, with concerns that investment in AI-driven drug discovery may not yield immediate returns [24]. As a result, multinational corporations with significant financial capacity lead innovation efforts while smaller pharmaceutical organisations struggle to compete.

2.2 Drivers of Technological Innovation Adoption

Despite the challenges, several factors drive the adoption of 4IR technologies in the South African pharmaceutical industry. One significant driver is the consumerisation of healthcare, which has increased demand for digital health solutions, including AI-assisted diagnostics, telemedicine, and online pharmaceutical services [24]. Patients increasingly prefer healthcare providers that offer digital services, prompting pharmaceutical organisations to invest in automation and data-driven decision-making. Growing cost-related challenges within the sector have also encouraged organisations to explore digital transformation to reduce operational inefficiencies and increase productivity [25]. Global competition (environment) has also acted as a catalyst for technological adoption. As multinational pharmaceutical organisations integrate AI-driven research

and automation, South African companies face increasing pressure to remain competitive by investing in similar technologies. Strategic investment is essential for local organisations to maintain relevance in the rapidly evolving landscape [23].

2.3 Strategy's Role in Fostering Innovation for Sustainable Business Practices

Pharmaceutical companies that adopt structured innovation strategies exhibit higher levels of sustainability and competitiveness. Huang (2021) highlights that leading organisations such as Pfizer, Johnson & Johnson, and Novartis sustain long-term growth by prioritising R&D investments and fostering collaborations with technology providers [26]. These companies have successfully integrated 4IR technologies to enhance production efficiency and reduce environmental impact. Emerging research suggests that innovation strategies must address technological factors and economic and regulatory considerations. Pharmaceutical organisations must develop policies that balance technological advancements with industry regulations and financial sustainability [7]. The practical implementation of innovation strategies ensures that organisations can optimise R&D efficiency while complying with sustainability standards.

2.4 Hypothesis Development Based on Literature

The development of the hypotheses in this study was informed by existing literature on R&D intensity, technological adoption, and innovation within the pharmaceutical industry, with a specific focus on emerging technologies such as 4IR. The first hypothesis, testing whether investment in 4IR technologies positively influences strategic innovation outcomes in the South African pharmaceutical industry, draws from studies on technology integration in developed markets, highlighting the need for comprehensive infrastructure and leadership engagement to drive meaningful innovation [2, 4]. The second hypothesis, exploring the impact of top management support on industry growth, is supported by literature on the role of leadership in facilitating the adoption of advanced technologies and aligning R&D with corporate strategy [3, 19]. The third hypothesis, which examines whether the allocation of advanced skills enhances innovation in pharmaceutical R&D, aligns with findings suggesting that while skilled personnel are vital, their effectiveness is contingent on organisational factors such as technological infrastructure and strategic alignment [7, 9]. These hypotheses are grounded in the theoretical framework provided by the TOE model [17].

3 Methodology

This study adopts a positivist research philosophy, employing a deductive approach to examine the relationships between R&D intensity, strategic leadership, and the adoption of 4IR technologies within the South African pharmaceutical industry. The deductive approach is considered appropriate for testing established theories and hypotheses derived from existing literature, allowing for the evaluation of measurable relationships between variables such as investment in emerging technologies, managerial support,

and innovation outcomes. Given the study's aim to assess these relationships quantitatively, a quantitative research design was deemed fitting. This design enables the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data, providing objective insights into the extent to which 4IR technologies are being adopted and their impact on innovation outcomes within the sector. A deductive approach is advantageous in this context, as it allows for the testing of hypotheses drawn from theoretical frameworks, rather than building new theory from exploratory findings. This warrants that the study's findings contribute to existing literature by supporting established models, providing insights for both practitioners and academics in the field. Following Saunders *et al.* (2019) research onion framework, a cross-sectional survey approach was employed, allowing for a structured and systematic analysis of industry professionals' perspectives on 4IR integration in pharmaceutical R&D [27].

3.1 Research Design and Sampling Strategy

A structured survey-based methodology was used to collect primary data from pharmaceutical industry professionals in South Africa. The target population included R&D professionals, senior executives, technology managers, and strategy specialists working within pharmaceutical organisations. These participants were selected based on their direct involvement in R&D decision-making, strategic planning, and technology adoption, ensuring that responses were derived from individuals with relevant expertise and industry knowledge. A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure a representative distribution of organisations across different categories, including multinational corporations, generic drug manufacturers, and biopharmaceutical organisations. This approach reduced selection bias and enhanced the generalisability of the findings. Given the relatively small and specialised nature of the South African pharmaceutical sector, a target sample size of 200 was initially set. However, 78 valid responses were obtained, reflecting the challenges of accessing a highly regulated and niche workforce. Despite the lower-than-anticipated response rate, the sample remains valid due to the specialised nature of the target respondents, who occupy decision-making roles within the industry [26, 28]. To address potential representativeness issues, the study adopted non-response mitigation strategies, including follow-up emails and extended survey distribution periods. Additionally, any incomplete data were excluded if there were any missing values, ensuring that incomplete responses were discarded so as not to affect the reliability of the dataset.

3.2 Data Collection and Instrumentation

The survey was administered electronically via the Qualtrics platform, supporting a secure and anonymous data collection process while maintaining the integrity of participant responses. The survey instrument was developed based on validated constructs from established literature, particularly drawing from Kruger and Steyn (2023) [19]. This approach allowed for the integration of well-supported theoretical frameworks, warranting that the constructs measured were relevant and aligned with the study's objectives. A seven-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 7 = Strongly

Agree) was utilised to capture respondents' perceptions of key constructs, enabling assessment of attitudes toward 4IR adoption and its impact on innovation performance within the pharmaceutical industry. Prior to full-scale data collection, a pilot study was conducted with five industry professionals to assess the clarity, reliability, and structure of the survey items. Feedback from the pilot study led to minor adjustments in question phrasing and alignment, ensuring that the instrument accurately captured the intended variables and met the study's objectives. This refinement process helped to improve the reliability of the instrument, addressing any ambiguities and ensuring that the survey would generate data that was both valid and meaningful for evaluating relationships.

3.3 Data Analysis Approach and Ethical Considerations

The collected data was analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics 29, applying descriptive, inferential, and multivariate statistical techniques to test the study's hypotheses. The first stage of analysis involved descriptive statistics to summarise respondent characteristics and assess general trends across key constructs. Correlation analysis was performed to examine relationships between R&D intensity, top management support, technology adoption, and strategic innovation outcomes. To determine the impact of 4IR technologies and leadership support on R&D innovation, multiple regression analysis was conducted. This technique allowed for the assessment of the predictive power of independent variables (investment in AI, biotechnology, and managerial support) on dependent variables (innovation performance and business growth). Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) were applied to identify potential multicollinearity issues, ensuring that independent variables were not excessively correlated, which could compromise regression results.

Reliability analysis was conducted using Cronbach's alpha, with an acceptable threshold of 0.7 to confirm the internal consistency of the constructs. Additionally, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was performed to assess construct validity and ensure that the survey items accurately measured the intended theoretical variables. Given the smaller sample size, robust standard errors were applied in regression models to enhance the accuracy of parameter estimates. While the final response rate was lower than anticipated, the study strived for methodological rigor by focusing on industry professionals directly engaged in strategic innovation and R&D leadership, thereby minimising concerns related to external validity.

This study received ethical approval from the research ethics committee at the university where the researchers were based, ensuring adherence to standard ethical protocols.

4 Findings

The descriptive statistics include the number of responses (n), mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and reliability estimates using Cronbach's alpha (α). The results indicate that Top Management Support for Growth Enablement has the highest mean score ($M = 5.82$, $SD = 11.41$), suggesting that respondents generally perceive top management

as moderately supportive of R&D-driven innovation. Technological Capabilities & Innovation in Pharmaceutical R&D received a lower mean score ($M = 5.73$, $SD = 11.44$), suggesting a more neutral or varied perception regarding the extent of technology adoption within the sector. Relative Advantage & Strategic Innovation Outcomes, which measure the perceived benefits of R&D intensity, yielded a mean of $M = 3.64$, $SD = 11.73$, implying mixed responses, with some scepticism toward the effectiveness of R&D investments in enhancing innovation outcomes.

Reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha yielded high values ($\alpha \approx 0.998$ across constructs), indicating strong internal consistency among survey items. However, the high VIF values, particularly for Technological Capabilities & Innovation in Pharmaceutical R&D ($VIF = 106.89$) and Top Management Support ($VIF = 123.07$), suggest possible multicollinearity concerns, indicating that some variables may be highly inter-related.

4.1 Construct Assessment

The mean score for Relative Advantage & Strategic Innovation Outcomes ($M = 3.64$, $SD = 11.73$) suggests a moderately varied perception of the extent to which R&D investments influence strategic innovation. The spreading in responses implies that while some participants perceive R&D intensity as beneficial, others remain neutral or slightly sceptical. This suggests that organisations, or even specific business units, may not fully realise the innovation potential of their R&D investments.

The mean score for Top Management Support for Growth Enablement ($M = 5.82$, $SD = 11.41$) indicates a generally positive but somewhat dispersed perception of leadership's role in fostering R&D growth. While top management support appears to be present, the variance in responses suggests inconsistencies across organisations. Some organisations may have strong leadership commitment to R&D, while others struggle to align strategic objectives and R&D priorities. The findings support the notion that managerial commitment is a key driver of R&D-driven innovation but remains an area requiring further development within the South African pharmaceutical industry.

The Technological Capabilities & Innovation in Pharmaceutical R&D construct received a mean score of $M = 5.73$, $SD = 11.44$, indicating that perceptions of technological readiness within the sector are varied. Given that South Africa's pharmaceutical industry has historically lagged in digital transformation, this finding aligns with previous research suggesting that adopting AI, biotechnology, and data-driven R&D processes remains limited. While some organisations appear to be integrating advanced technologies, the industry landscape remains fragmented, with gaps in capability development and infrastructure.

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

To assess the research hypotheses, t-tests were conducted to evaluate whether each construct's mean significantly deviated from the neutral midpoint (4 on a 7-point Likert scale). Pearson correlation analysis was used to determine relationships between key constructs.

The first hypothesis tested whether investment in 4IR technologies positively influences strategic innovation outcomes within the South African pharmaceutical industry. The results show a negligible mean correlation (0.006) between investment and innovation outcomes, with a non-significant t-test ($p > 0.05$). Thus, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating that investment in 4IR technologies does not significantly impact innovation outcomes. This suggests that additional factors, such as leadership engagement, workforce skills, and regulatory barriers, may be needed to drive strategic innovation.

The second hypothesis examined whether top management support for 4IR technologies positively influences industry growth. The results indicate a significant positive correlation (mean correlation = 0.520, $p < 0.01$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0). This supports the idea that strong managerial commitment to R&D is crucial for leveraging 4IR technologies and fostering a culture of innovation. Organisations lacking executive support may struggle to align R&D investments with corporate strategy, limiting innovation.

The third hypothesis tested whether allocating advanced skills within organisations enhances innovation in pharmaceutical R&D. The findings show a weak correlation (mean correlation = 0.019) with innovation, and the t-test results were non-significant ($p > 0.05$). We fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), suggesting that skilled personnel alone are insufficient to drive innovation without the necessary technological infrastructure, strategic alignment, and funding. Organisations must bridge skill gaps with improved infrastructure and effectively integrate expertise into R&D processes.

Table 1. Hypothesis overview.

Hypothesis	Statement	Statistical result	Decision
H1	Investing in 4IR technologies positively influences strategic innovation outcomes.	Non-significant ($p > 0.05$)	Fail to reject H_0
H2	Top management support for 4IR technologies positively impacts growth.	Significant ($p = 0.006$)	Reject H_0
H3	Allocation of advanced skills enhances pharmaceutical R&D innovation.	Non-significant ($p > 0.05$)	Fail to reject H_0

5 Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to assess the impact of R&D intensity on strategic decision-making and innovation within the South African pharmaceutical industry, with a focus on the role of 4IR technologies. While AI and biotechnology are widely recognised for their potential to enhance pharmaceutical R&D [4, 8, 28, 29], the findings indicate that investment in these technologies alone does not directly lead to strategic innovation. Instead, the study highlights that top management support and strategic leadership play a more crucial role in enabling successful R&D-driven innovation. This challenges the assumption that technological integration alone drives innovation

outcomes. Effective digital transformation requires not only investment but also leadership commitment, regulatory adaptation, and workforce reskilling to optimise the use of new technologies within existing R&D frameworks.

Novel technologies may offer transformative potential in pharmaceutical R&D, but their effectiveness is contingent upon the organisation's capacity to integrate them into existing frameworks. Without addressing structural inefficiencies, regulatory barriers, and skill shortages, technology adoption is unlikely to yield meaningful innovation.

In contrast to the limited effect of technology investment, top management support emerged as a driver of industry growth and innovation adoption. Organisations where executives actively engaged with R&D strategy and technology implementation were more successful in integrating 4IR tools and achieving positive innovation outcomes. This finding aligns with existing literature on strategic leadership and innovation, underscoring that organisational commitment, rather than financial investment alone, is essential for technological success. Strong leadership fosters a culture of innovation, enables policy development, and ensures that technology investments are strategically aligned with corporate goals. The positive relationship between executive support and technology adoption highlights the need for leadership-driven digital transformation strategies in the pharmaceutical sector.

The study also identified technological capability gaps as a major barrier to pharmaceutical innovation. While respondents acknowledged the importance of technology in enhancing drug discovery, clinical trials, and personalised medicine, they expressed concerns about inadequate infrastructure, regulatory delays, and a shortage of skilled professionals in digital health and computational drug discovery. The weak correlation between technological capability and innovation outcomes suggests that many organisations are not yet effectively leveraging 4IR technologies, likely due to insufficient digital literacy and fragmented adoption strategies. Proficiency in digital literacy is critical when adopting new technologies; without these skills, companies struggle to utilise modern methods effectively, leading to scattered efforts and missed opportunities in strategic implementation.

This study contributes to the body of research on digital transformation in emerging markets, offering empirical insights into the intersection of R&D and 4IR adoption in South Africa's pharmaceutical industry. While extensive research has focused on pharmaceutical innovation in developed economies, limited studies have explored how emerging economies navigate digital transformation amidst structural constraints. By applying the amended TOE model, the study provides further understanding of the factors influencing 4IR adoption in pharmaceutical R&D. However, the findings suggest that these models alone may not fully explain the South African context. Given the significant role of leadership in technology adoption, a leadership-driven innovation model, such as the Dynamic Capabilities Framework, could offer additional explanatory power for future research.

The findings have implications for both industry practitioners and policymakers. The weak relationship between technology investment and innovation outcomes suggests that pharmaceutical organisations must adopt a more strategic approach to 4IR adoption. Rather than viewing emerging technologies as isolated investments, organi-

sations should focus on aligning these technologies with leadership-driven strategic objectives, business models, and long-term R&D priorities. Strengthening executive leadership in R&D strategy and digital literacy is critical. Given the positive relationship between top management support and industry growth, organisations should invest in leadership development programs focused on digital transformation, regulatory navigation, and AI-driven decision-making. Such programs can help industry executives integrate 4IR technologies effectively into corporate strategy and innovation processes.

Addressing technological capability gaps is another key consideration for industry stakeholders. The sector can invest in upskilling programs that equip professionals with the necessary competencies to work with AI-assisted drug discovery tools and biotechnological advancements. Public-private partnerships can play a role in encouraging industry-academic collaborations to develop specialised training programs in digital health and computational medicine. Additionally, financial incentives, such as tax credits for companies investing in workforce development, could accelerate the adoption of AI and biotechnology in pharmaceutical R&D. These initiatives would help bridge the digital skills gap, ensuring that organisations have access to a workforce capable of leveraging 4IR technologies effectively [12].

Regulatory reform is also essential to support innovation in the pharmaceutical sector. Policymakers should consider streamlining regulatory approvals for AI-based drug discovery and digital clinical trials to accelerate the innovation process. From a Society 5.0 perspective, cross-disciplinary collaboration could further enhance healthcare, underpinned by human-centric innovation.

6 Conclusion

This study provides insights into the relationship between R&D intensity, strategic decision-making, and 4IR technology adoption in the South African pharmaceutical industry. While investment in technology alone does not guarantee innovation, top management support emerges as a crucial enabler of industry growth. The findings suggest that technological capability gaps persist, necessitating targeted interventions in workforce training, strategic alignment, and regulatory adaptation.

Future research should examine longitudinal data to assess how R&D intensity influences innovation outcomes over time. A time-series analysis would allow for more accurate predictions of industry trends, particularly in the context of 4IR technology adoption. Also, research should include comparative studies between South Africa and other emerging markets, such as India and Brazil, to identify common barriers and best practices in pharmaceutical R&D.

6.1 Limitations

Despite its contributions, the study faced several limitations. The sample size of 78 responses, though valid for a niche industry, limits generalisability. Future research should aim to expand the sample size, potentially by partnering with pharmaceutical

industry bodies to increase survey participation. The study primarily relied on self-reported survey data, which may be subject to response bias.

Acknowledgments and Disclosure of Interests. We want to thank our dedicated information specialist and the ethical committee for their support in this research. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to this research study.

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